

XORIYIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

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THE PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATING TERMS FROM ENGLISH INTO UZBEK

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***Abstract:** This article explores the challenges and methods involved in translating English terms into Uzbek, considering the linguistic and cultural implications of terminology translation. The article provides an overview of terminology as a field, examines common translation challenges, and evaluates various translation techniques. The research is based on empirical analysis of translated terms, highlighting effective strategies for ensuring accuracy and consistency in specialized translation.*

***Key words:** terminology, transcription, transliteration, descriptive translation, equivalence*

Introduction. Translation of terms has never been so crucial for academic and professional fields as it is now. Due to globalization, people are becoming increasingly reliant on shared knowledge, which is, in turn, rising the demand for understanding, creating and exchanging new concepts in various domains. In our country, the need for precise term translation is particularly relevant due to the efforts to modernize and integrate with international scientific and technological developments.

It is difficult to imagine science without terms, as they constitute majority part of scientific texts. Each and every new notion that is being introduced as the result of technological advancements is given a certain name, consistently increasing the number of terms. All of these facts unequivocally show the need for a distinct field of research, with precise phrases as its subject. It is a recent accomplishment to comprehend terminology as a separate science, although this was not always the case. Specifically, terminology was regarded as a component of lexicology, it was only at the beginning of XX century did terminology come into view as a separate domain. However, the establishment of terminology as a distinct scientific discipline has not led to the development of generalizing theoretical work with a clear formulation and solution of problems related to the components of a scientific discipline. The reasons for this are evident in the interdisciplinary nature of this field of knowledge. The development of terminology as a science was initiated by the Russian terminologist Dmitriy Lotte and the Austrian scientist Eugen Wüster, who independently published their first terminological works in 1931. Over the years, theories and framework of terminology has been researched extensively and polished, and today, we generally understand the study of specialized words and phrases used within a specific field as

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an ultimate definition of terminology. Terminology, as a linguistic field, is mainly concerned with the followings:

- examining ideas and concept structures that are applied in a field or activity;
- determining the terminology used to describe concepts;
- establishing connections between terms in several languages when a term is bilingual or multilingual;
- generating new terminology in databases, gathering terms on paper, or maintaining terminology databases as needed

Terms lie at the core of the terminological research, as this branch focuses on analyzing their origin, meaning, structure and functional features. This article also aims to discuss what poses challenges in the translation of terms, especially from English into Uzbek and suggest a few methods that can be utilized to improve the efficiency of translation.

Literature review. Multiple studies have been conducted to develop theoretical framework of terminology, to discover its practical implications and to define the notion of “term”. The name of the Austrian linguist and scientist Eugen Wuster, who is regarded as the founder of scientific terminology because of his work that significantly contributed to the formation of modern terminology, is linked to the development of the discipline of terminology. In his doctoral dissertation, he established various principles for dealing with terms, outlined the fundamental guidelines for the methodology of processing words, and made several arguments for the systematization of approaches to working with terminology. He claims that the following four linguists are the founders of terminological theory: the first scientist to consider the systematic nature of special words was Alfred Scholmann, a German physicist; the first scientist to recognize the systematic nature of language was the Swiss linguist Ferdinand de Saussure; Ernest Dresen, a Russian, was among the first to see the value of standardizing; and a British scientist working for UNESCO. One individual who significantly contributed to the internationalization of the vocabulary was E. Holmstorm. It is also important to credit Dmitriy Lotte as the founder of terminology, as his contribution was huge in understanding the notion of term. The main requirements for the term were developed by a prominent linguist D.S. Lotte. He proposed that a term should be structural and follow these requirements: *non-specificity, brevity, unambiguousness, clarity, simplicity, comprehensibility, degree of applicability.*

Translation problems of terms is not a new area of research in Uzbekistan. A lot of researchers have looked into the matter and came up with their own theories about

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mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

terminology, tried to give solutions for the existing problems of terminology. One of them is Paluanova H.D who conducted a comparative research on ecologic terms in Uzbek, English and Karakalpak in her doctoral thesis in 2016. Rahmatullayeva F.K. focused on various aspects of medical terms, their translation, expression and formation and published several articles on this topic. Fatullayeva K.R. is also noted for her works in defining and understanding the notion of term. The main objective of this article is to further analyze the challenges of translation scientific terms, and come up with solutions to these problems.

Research Method and Process. This research was carried out by means of comparative analysis of English-Uzbek terms. This research method was used to identify the equivalents of English terms in Uzbek, compare and contrast the existing translation and to find out the possible translation techniques that can be used in the process of terminological translation. Comparative analysis facilitated the identification of a number of linguistic and cultural nuances observed in the process of translating terms. The data was gathered online from Oxford Learner's Dictionary and from guidebook named "Atamalarning izohli lug'ati". A group of common English terms were chosen and their equivalents in Uzbek were identified, after which the translation methods used in the process of translation were determined.

Results and Discussion. One of the most serious shortcomings of the terminology, according to D.S. Lotte, is that the meaning of a term varies from context to context. He emphasized the crucial role of context in understanding the meaning of a term and highlighted potential issues arising from variations in interpretation depending on the situation. As there are plenty of context-dependent terms, it is important to figure out what context they are used in and what domain they belong to. For instance, the term "*pitch*" refers to the playing field if used in the context of sports and physical education (*maydon*). However, in the context of other domains, it denotes totally different notions: in physics, it denotes the distance between threads in a screw (*mix aylanmalari orasidagi masofa*); in music, it refers to the frequency of a sound (*tovush balandligi*); in the field of sales and business, it denotes a persuasive presentation to sell something (*savdo taqdimoti*).

Alongside with contextual differences, cultural differences also play a crucial role in the process of terminological translation. Since language and culture are closely related, translating terminology involves more than just changing the vocabulary; it also entails adapting ideas to the target language's conceptual and cultural framework. Some terms in English are based on Western cultural or scientific perspectives, which may not have direct equivalents in Uzbek due to different ways

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mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

of categorizing knowledge. The English term privacy is challenging to translate into Uzbek because the cultural understanding of personal space and private life differs. In Uzbek, the closest equivalent is *shaxsiy daxlsizlik* (personal inviolability), but this term leans more towards legal protection rather than the broader cultural sense of privacy.

More often than not religious beliefs also interfere into the process of translation. As Uzbek community is largely Islamic, it is quite challenging to translate them directly. A good case in point is Christmas, which is a type of religious celebration of Christians. Since it has no equivalent in Uzbek, it is usually translated as "*Rojdestvo*" (borrowed from Russian) or it is just used alongside with its definition (descriptive translation). Another example is the term "*zakot*", an obligatory almsgiving in Islam. Although it is widely used in countries whose religion is Islam, it is generally an alien phenomenon for most European and Western communities, including the English, whose religion is not primarily Islam. Hence, it is preferable to translate these terms through descriptive translation, clearly pointing out their meaning and function. Another significant challenge of terminological translation is the lack of equivalence. It is difficult to find an Uzbek alternative to all the terms, especially the ones that is being established in the language because of recent advancements in technology and science. For instance, a few years ago, our country experienced a temporary loss of electricity supply – *blackout*. As such thing has never happened before, there was no equivalent to express this term in Uzbek language, so it was immediately borrowed through transcription as *blekout* into Uzbek. In such cases when there is no direct equivalent, the best option is to translate the word through transliteration or transcription.

Roman Jakobson (2005) noted that there is no word or lexicon unit that cannot be translated from one language into another. It is always possible to find equivalent or alternative. Translation of terms, though challenging, is not impossible. One way or another, it is always possible to find a solution and achieve effective translation.

Conclusion. As our world continues to grow, new concepts, items and notion also go on to increase consistently. Scientific and technological advancements, every aspect of our life is closely associated with terms. Therefore, translation of terms remain as one of the most topical areas of research. In this article, several problems translators face while translating terms have been discussed, which included the contextual and cultural differences, lack of equivalence. Relevant solutions to these problems were presented and the translation techniques by which translation can be carried out easily have been identified. Although terms are not fixed and bound to

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mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

changes because of the societal, academic, scientific and technological reasons, they are dependent on their context in most cases and there are some terms that are specific to certain cultures and religions, translation techniques, such as transliteration, transcription, descriptive translation and adaptation or adoption usually ensure the smooth and coherent translation of terms from English into Uzbek. The perspective for further investigation is to further analyze the translation techniques that are applied in the process of translating terms, and their translation not only from English, but also from other languages as well.

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